

IN-PLANE PERMEABILITY CHARACTERISATION OF MATS AND FABRICS USING SRIM

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the development of a method for permeability measurement that can be applied on line during any constant flowrate liquid moulding process. The conventional flow visualisation method is replaced by pressure monitoring within the mould cavity. The technique is demonstrated for two nominally isotropic reinforcements and results are compared to those derived from conventional bench top methods. Close agreement with previous test results indicates that the method has excellent potential as a rapid means of mat/fabric characterisation under realistic process conditions.

INTRODUCTION

This paper concerns a study of flow phenomena during structural reaction injection moulding (SRIM) with an emphasis on materials characterisation for flow modelling. Specifically, SRIM involves impingement mixing at the point of injection and unlike the related process of resin transfer moulding (RTM), may involve some turbulent flow in the immediate vicinity of the injection gate. To maintain optimum mixing conditions for SRIM the resin needs to be injected at closely controlled (usually constant) volume flow rates. The viscosity of the mixed resin system is typically an order of magnitude lower than that found in RTM. High flow rates and low viscosities may cause the flow to remain turbulent for a significant part of mould filling and for non-Newtonian flows a modified flow model is required [1,2]. Despite these potential limitations, Darcy flow has been applied to describe a number of SRIM processes, with success reported, for example by Lee *et al*[3] and more recently by Couniot *et al*[4].

A number of in-plane permeability studies have been reported and can be divided into two general categories: those which employ rectilinear flow, as described by Gebart[5], Parnas[6] and Gauvin[7], and those using radial flow as described in detail by Adams *et al* [8-11] and Chan[12-13]. Either method may employ constant injection pressure or constant injection flow rates. The advantages of using rectilinear flow include simplicity of data analysis and, when constant injection pressures are used, there is a practical advantage in being able to take an averaged velocity of the advancing flow front. The main disadvantages are that more than one test is required to characterise the in-plane

permeabilities and that "racetracking" may occur at the edges of the fibre sample due to high local porosities arising from an imperfect fit between the sample and sample holder. Methods which use radial flow from a point source require more complex analysis of experimental data, particularly when the fluid is injected at constant pressure, but have the advantage that the both of the in-plane, principal permeabilities can be deduced from the results of a single experiment. Because radial measurement of the in-plane permeabilities usually relies upon visual assessment of the flow front velocities, low stiffness moulds constructed from glass or Plexiglass are often used. This limits the fluid flow rates and pressure to at least an order of magnitude lower than those typically of industrial SRIM processes [11]. Such bench-top rigs are usually limited in the maximum fibre packing fraction which can be achieved. Since fibre compaction forces can be at least as significant as fluid pressures in determining mould deflections, practical testing using radial flow methods particularly is often limited to values below those used in current industrial practice.

In order to address some of the issues involved in generating permeability data which is applicable to SRIM it has been attempted to develop a method of deriving the information on-line from a typical moulding operation. This offers the potential advantages of operating conditions (fluid pressures, flow rates and fibre fractions) which closely reproduce those used in current industrial practice. The paper presents an analysis of radial flow in anisotropic porous media to establish a method for in-plane permeability measurement based upon constant volume flow rate and the in-mould pressure history. The results are compared with permeability data obtained from both radial flow and rectilinear flow bench rigs.

PERMEABILITY MEASUREMENTS

Growing activity in process modelling for liquid composite moulding operations has led to an explosion of interest in techniques for characterisation of reinforcement in-plane permeabilities. Conventional measurements are made using transparent moulds and model fluids such as silicone oils and corn syrup. The majority of published data have been produced at relatively low fluid pressure and low flow rates, due to limits imposed by mould deflections. High volume moulding operations such as SRIM typically impose pressures and flowrates an order of magnitude higher than these values.

Theory

Assuming that the pressure is known at two locations along the principal axes of flow, the steady state or *wetted* permeability values are obtained by solution of the following equations:

$$\frac{Q}{2\pi h\beta} = - \frac{k_x (P_{x1} - P_{x0})}{\mu \ln(r_{x1} / r_{x0})} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{Q\beta}{2\pi h} = - \frac{k_y (P_{y1} - P_{y0})}{\mu \ln(r_{y1} / r_{y0})} \quad (2)$$

Where β is the aspect ratio of the ellipse formed by the impregnated region, directly linked to the degree of anisotropy, α , by the relationship [14]:

$$\beta^2 = \alpha \equiv \left(\frac{r_y}{r_x} \right)^2 = \frac{k_y}{k_x} \quad (3)$$

Similarly, assuming that the pressure at the flow front is atmospheric, and that resin flows from a point source, the pressure at a known point along the x axis of flow can be expressed as:

$$p_x = \frac{1}{2} \lambda_x \ln t + \frac{1}{2} \lambda_x \ln \left(\frac{Q}{h \epsilon \pi \beta} \right) - \lambda_x \ln r_x \quad (4)$$

Where:

$$\lambda_x = \frac{Q \mu}{2 \pi \beta h \epsilon k_x} \quad (5)$$

From Eqn (4) it can be seen that a plot of p vs. $\frac{1}{2} \ln(t)$ will yield a straight line whose gradient is λ_x . A similar expression can be derived for λ_y , hence k_x and k_y can be derived. These values of permeability are the transient or *wetting* permeability, accounting for flow of resin into a dry preform.

Experimental Procedure

The proposed experimental method was tested using a commercial two component RIM machine, (Krauss Maffei NBC-RIM-STAR 40), injecting into the centre of a steel bowl-shaped mould. A 200 tonne down-stroke press prevented the mould shells from separating as a result of internal mould pressures. The minimum thickness of the hardened steel mould halves was 40mm and deflection was considered negligible.

The mould was instrumented with an array of thermocouples and pressure transducers as shown in Fig. 1. 8mm diameter miniature pressure transducers (RDP Engineering) were located along each of a pair of orthogonal axes. Transducer calibration was carried out *in situ* to avoid systematic errors. To monitor the temperature history inside the mould, K-type (NiCr/NiAl) thermocouples were positioned opposite each of the pressure transducers with the sensor tip protruding into the centre line of the cavity.

Figure 1. Cross-section of bowl shaped mould.

The resin system used was a two part, amine cured epoxy (Shell DX6008/DX6511), mixed in a ratio of resin to curing agent of 4:1 by mass. Controlled heating of the resin, curing agent and mould

allowed experiments to be carried out over a range of temperatures under approximately isothermal injection conditions. The metering pumps and mixing head of the SRIM facility allowed for a range of controlled flow rates from 100 g/s to 300 g/s. The exact flow rate was established by preceding each series of experiments with a number of timed and weighed short shots. To minimise reinforcement compaction under fluid pressure at the injection point and trans-planar flow a 20mm diameter hole was punched from the centre of the reinforcement.

The theoretical analysis considered radial flow only. Flow into the base of the mould was considered approximately radial and for the majority of tests resin injection was terminated once the base was filled. A PC based data acquisition system recorded the pressure and temperature histories at the sensor locations. The results were compared with data generated by Bulmer[14] using a stiffened Plexiglass mould arranged for radial flow similar to the arrangement proposed by Adams *et al.*

Experimental Results and Discussion

The mould geometry limited experiments to materials with only a small degree of anisotropy. For highly anisotropic materials, the flow front along the semi-minor axis would not develop sufficiently enough for pressure data to be acquired before the semi-major axis flow front had reached the edge of the base and flow ceased to be radial. A further limiting factor was present in the reinforcing feature in the base of the mould where the cavity thickness changed from 10mm to 6mm. This acts, in effect, as the injection gate diameter for the region of interest. The analysis assumes flow from a line source, which is not possible in practice. However from observation of tests on the bench rig the flow front quickly converges to a stable ellipse of constant aspect ratio[14]. For estimating the permeability using Eqn (4) the time at start of injection was normalised to compensate for the additional time taken to fill the reinforcing feature.

The permeabilities of two types of nominally isotropic fibre matting were examined:

- Chomorat Rovicore 450/A5/450. This is a sandwich of chopped strand mat with a thermoplastic polyester fibre core stitched together with polyester thread, the polyester core constitutes 22% by mass of the mat. This material was selected for preliminary trials due to its ease of handling and good draping properties.
- Vetrotex Unifilo U750-450 continuous filament random mat. This material is used extensively in liquid composite moulding and permeability data from a range of studies is available for comparison [14].

Although materials are nominally plane isotropic the analysis presupposed a degree of anisotropy and care was taken to keep the warp alignments the same for each layer of the preform, and to align the mats with the same axes as the pressure transducers. Analysis of the data was performed using Eqns (1), (2) and Eqn (4) to compare the wetted and wetting permeabilities.

The tests were performed over a range of temperatures and flow rates to test the assumptions listed earlier. Fig. 2. shows the *pressure vs. $\frac{1}{2}\ln$ time* relationship for the Vetrotex reinforcement which illustrates the linear relation and supports the initial assumptions. The results also show an apparent anisotropy in the preform, since the x-axis pressure rise occurred in advance of that on the y-axis (i.e. the reinforcement weft direction). This phenomenon was apparent in all tests carried out on U750-450 taken from the same roll. However, replicate tests performed on a different batch indicated a preferred orientation in the y-direction. This variability is inherent in the manufacture of such reinforcements and has been noted previously[14].

Linear regression was used to determine the slope of each *pressure vs. 1/2 ln time* graph, hence the wetting permeabilities. Once the flow front crosses the second pressure transducer along each axis, the pressure drop across each pair of transducers should remain constant for the remainder of the injection period, also shown in Fig. 2. The averaged pressure drop over this period along each axis was used to determine the wetted permeability.

One of the principal assumptions of the method is that the viscosity of the resin system remains constant throughout the filling stage. It has been suggested that the average viscosity remains almost unchanged for the first thirty seconds of the moulding cycle before increasing rapidly as the component cures [15]. The average value of the viscosity over the period 3-6 seconds (for a 4 second injection period) was taken for the permeability determination. This period was chosen to ensure that resin temperatures, rather than reinforcement or mould temperatures dominated the viscosity estimates. It is recognised, of course, that the flow front viscosity will differ significantly from that at the gate for non-isothermal conditions.

Figure 2. Mould cavity pressure drop on principal axes during SRIM impregnation

Effects of Test Temperature

Fig. 3 shows the results from tests performed on U750/450 over a range of temperatures under nominally isothermal injection conditions from 70-120°C (the maximum practicable resin storage temperature) and non-isothermal tests from 140-180°C. The non-isothermal tests were made at resin storage temperatures of 120°C. For these experiments the flow rate was maintained at 118g/s and the porosity at 58%. The isothermal results from tests below 110°C are reasonably consistent at an average value of $1.6 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2$ (at 58% porosity). For temperatures above 110°C the permeability estimates begin to drop. This may be due to the under-estimation of resin viscosity at the higher temperatures due to a combination of the simple thermal model and the temperature averaging method. Clearly there is scope for further work in this area.

Figure 3. Effect of test temperature on apparent in-plane permeabilities

Effects of Flow Rate

Tests were carried out using U750/450 over a range of flow rates from 100g/s to 300g/s at an isothermal temperature of 100°C and a porosity of 58%. The results are shown in Fig. 4. Within the range of experimental scatter there was no discernible trend with increasing flow rate.

Figure 4. Effect of resin flow rate on apparent in-plane permeabilities

Comparison with Previous Results

Fig. 5 compares the wetted and wetting permeabilities derived from an equivalent series of tests for the Chomorat Rovicore 450/A5/450 mat with data generated using a radial flow Plexiglass mould by Bulmer[14]. Practical limitations meant that for comparative tests between the bench rig and the SRIM facility the range of porosities tested was different. The sensitivity of the pressure transducers

on the SRIM facility limited tests to porosities below 72% while the Plexiglass mould could not be used at porosities less than 59% due to mould flexing.

Figure 5. Comparison of in-plane permeabilities by SRIM techniques with previous results for Chomorat Rovicore

The results of tests on U750/450 are shown in Fig. 6 together with collective data taken from tests using the radial flow bench rig[14] and a rectilinear flow rig[16]. The results derived from the SRIM tests are generally in good agreement with the collective data from previous work at low pressures and low flow rates. The results also show that for these materials and process conditions the difference between the wetting and wetted permeabilities is negligible.

Figure 6. Comparison of in-plane permeabilities by SRIM techniques with previous results for Vetrotex U750-450

Since there is no visual inspection of the flow pattern, in the method described above where there are pressure transducers along only one pair of axes, the principal axes of the resulting ellipse must be known *a priori*. In the present study this was done simply by carrying out short shots for each batch of reinforcement.

SUMMARY

A method for the determination of principal permeability values in an anisotropic fibre reinforcement has been described. Values of wetting and wetted permeabilities have been measured successfully, using data taken directly from an SRIM mould. The results are in good agreement with existing data derived from conventional low pressure test rigs and suggest that existing permeability data from these rigs can be applied with reasonable confidence in high speed processes. By using the method described, permeabilities can be measured conveniently under more typical process conditions and at lower porosities than can generally be achieved using conventional laboratory equipment.

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